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**DATA-DRIVEN DECISION MAKING IN QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS
(ISO 9001:2015): A STATISTICAL APPROACH AND CASE STUDIES**

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Abstract. *In the context of digitalization and increasing demands on the effectiveness of quality management systems (QMS), data-driven decision-making using statistical analysis methods is becoming increasingly important. This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of applying a statistical approach to quality management, including methods and assessment of the significance of results using p-value. Particular attention is paid to the interpretation of p-value as a tool for confirming the statistical significance of the relationships between quality indicators, production process parameters, and the effectiveness of management decisions. The study demonstrates that the use of statistical methods allows for more objective process assessment, timely detection of deviations, and minimization of the likelihood of making erroneous management decisions. Practical cases from the industrial sector demonstrate a decrease in defect rates, a reduction in process variability, and an increase in the resilience of the production system through the use of data analytics and digital tools. The scientific novelty of the study lies in its comprehensive consideration of p-value and statistical analysis as elements of QMS intellectualization in the context of Industry 4.0. The practical significance of the work is determined by the possibility of applying the proposed approaches to improve the efficiency of quality control, the validity of management decisions and the competitiveness of industrial enterprises.*

Keywords: *quality management system, data-driven decision making, p-value, statistical significance, statistical analysis, SPC, quality control, digitalization, Industry 4.0, process management.*

In the context of the digital transformation of industry and intensifying competition in global markets, the ability of organizations to make informed management decisions is particularly important. Modern enterprises, especially in the metallurgical industry, operate in a highly uncertain environment, where even minor deviations in process parameters can lead to significant economic losses.

The quality management system regulated by ISO 9001:2015 is focused on ensuring process stability and continuous improvement. One of the key principles of this standard is decision-making based on facts and data. However, in practice, this principle is often implemented formally: companies collect significant amounts of data but do not always use it for in-depth analysis and to substantiate management decisions [1-4].

In this regard, the use of statistical methods that not only record changes in indicators but also assess their reliability is particularly relevant. Central to these methods is statistical hypothesis testing and the associated p-value. This tool allows one to answer a fundamental question: are the observed changes the result of management intervention or did they occur randomly?

It should be noted that in industrial practice, there is often a discrepancy between actual improvements and their statistical confirmation. For example, a reduction in defect rates may be documented at the performance level, but without statistical evaluation, it is impossible to definitively assert that this improvement is sustainable and reproducible.

The aim of the article is to develop in students and practitioners a systematic understanding of the role of statistical methods in quality management, as well as the skills of interpreting the results of data analysis when making management decisions.

Its practical significance lies in its focus on real-world production situations, including examples from metallurgical companies such as QARMET JSC. This allows students not only to master the theoretical material but also to learn how to apply it in a real-world economic environment.

A quality management system is a set of interrelated organizational management elements aimed at ensuring consistent product quality and customer satisfaction. According to the ISO 9001:2015 standard, an organization must not only control processes but also systematically analyze the data generated during their operation.

Of particular importance is paragraph 9.1.3, which regulates data analysis and evaluation. This requirement requires the organization to: determine which data needs to be analyzed; use appropriate analytical methods; and apply the results of the analysis to decision-making and process improvement. Thus, data becomes not just a reporting element, but a management tool.

The key model of quality management is the PDCA cycle, which includes four stages: Plan — defining goals and hypotheses; Do — implementing changes; Check — analyzing results; Act — making decisions. The Check stage involves data analysis, and this is where statistical methods become necessary. Without a quantitative assessment of the results, it is impossible to objectively determine the effectiveness of the implemented changes.

Statistical analysis is based on hypothesis testing. In the context of quality management, two hypotheses are formulated: the null hypothesis (H_0) — there are no changes, the observed differences are random; the alternative hypothesis (H_1) — the changes are due to an impact and are systemic in nature. Management decisions involve choosing between these hypotheses. This requires considering the possibility of errors: a type I error is rejecting H_0 when it is actually true (a false positive); a type II error is accepting H_0 when it is false (a false negative). Quality management requires minimizing these errors, as they can lead to incorrect management decisions.

The central element of hypothesis testing is the p- value. What is a p- value (significance level) ? It's the probability of obtaining the observed result (or a more extreme one) if the null hypothesis H_0 is actually true. The key idea is that we're not testing whether the hypothesis is true, but rather how much our data contradicts H_0 .

Interpretation of statistical significance in QMS:

p- value	Interpretation	Management decision	Risk level
$p \leq 0.01$	Very high reliability	Scaling the solution	Short
$0.01 < p \leq 0.05$	The result is statistically significant.	Implementation under control	Moderate
$0.05 < p \leq 0.10$	Borderline significance	Additional data collection	Increased
$p > 0.10$	Insufficient evidence	Refusal to scale	High

The presented data show that the interpretation of p- value in the quality management system should take into account not only statistical significance, but also the level of management risk associated with the implementation of solutions.

A very important clarification (a common mistake). Incorrect: the p- value is the probability that the hypothesis is true. Correct: the p- value is the probability of observing such data if the hypothesis is already considered true. The p- value is a quantitative measure of how much the observed data contradict the null hypothesis: the smaller the p- value, the stronger the grounds for rejecting it.

The p- value is interpreted as follows: a small p-value indicates that the data contradict the null hypothesis; a large p- value indicates that there is insufficient evidence to reject it. In practice, a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ is used. If the p- value ≤ 0.05 , the null hypothesis is rejected.

Despite the widespread use of the p- value, its interpretation is often fraught with errors: identifying the p- value with the probability of a hypothesis being true; ignoring the effect size; making decisions solely based on the threshold value; underestimating the influence of sample size. Understanding these limitations is a prerequisite for the correct use of statistical methods in quality management.

Using p- values in a quality management system allows for the transition from intuitive to informed decisions. However, it is important to understand that statistical significance does not always equate to practical or economic effectiveness. Therefore, decision-making should consider: statistical reliability (p- value); economic indicators (ROI, costs, profit); and expert judgment.

In modern educational approaches, the case method is particularly important, allowing students to connect theoretical knowledge with real-life management situations. In the context of quality management systems, cases serve as a tool for developing students' skills in interpreting data, critically analyzing results, and making management decisions under uncertainty. Cases based on real industrial practice are particularly valuable, as they reflect the complexity and multidimensionality of quality management processes.

QARMET JSC 's production site. The goal is to reduce defective products. The following data were obtained:

Indicator	Before implementation	After implementation
Marriage rate	5.0%	4.2%
Sample size	10,000	10,000
p- value	—	0.08

An actual reduction in defect rates of 0.8% is observed. However, the p- value is 0.08, which exceeds the standard significance level of $\alpha=0.05$. The obtained results do not allow us to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the observed reduction in defect rates may be due to random factors. This case demonstrates a fundamentally important situation: the presence of an improvement in indicators does not always mean the presence of a statistically significant effect. Under conditions of uncertainty, it is recommended to: continue data collection; increase the sample size; re-run the analysis; and avoid making radical decisions based on current results.

QARMET JSC has implemented a digital quality control system, incorporating machine vision technologies and artificial intelligence elements. The goal of the implementation is to reduce the rate of defective products and associated economic losses. Initial data:

Indicator	Before implementation	After implementation
Production volume, tons/month	50,000	50,000
Marriage rate	5.0%	3.8%

Losses per 1 ton of defective products	120,000 tenge	120,000 tenge
Implementation costs	—	180,000,000 tenge
p- value	—	0.02

Economic effect formula: $E = (D_{before} - D_{after}) \times V \times C$. where: D_{before} —defect rate before implementation; D_{after} —defect rate after implementation; V —production volume; C —cost of losses per unit of defect. Calculation for the case of JSC "QARMET". Initial data: defect reduction: 5.0% → 3.8%; production volume: 50,000 tons/ month; cost of losses: 120,000 tenge /t. Calculation: $(0.05 - 0.038) \times 50,000 \times 120,000$; $0.012 \times 50,000 \times 120,000$; $600 \times 120,000 = 72,000,000$ The economic impact of implementing a digital quality control system amounted to 72 million tenge per month, confirming the high efficiency of integrating data analytics into quality management processes. This case demonstrates synergies between statistical significance (p- value); economic efficiency (ROI); and technological development. Recommended: scaling the system to other areas; integration with digital management platforms; and inclusion of metrics in the KPI system. The most informed management decisions are made by simultaneously considering statistical reliability and economic efficiency.

JSC QFRMET recorded a decrease in defects: from 5.0% to 4.6 %, p- value = 0.30. Despite the positive trend in this indicator, the p- value indicates a high probability of randomness. Making scaling decisions based on such data could lead to: unjustified investments; distorted performance assessments; and decreased trust in the management system. This case demonstrates the danger of making decisions based on visually observable but statistically unconfirmed changes.

Comparative analysis of the effectiveness of solutions using three case studies:

Case	p- value	ROI	Economic effect	Management decision
Case 1	0.08	12%	Short	Continue observation
Case 2	0.02	380%	High	Scaling
Case 3	0.30	5%	Minor	Refusal to implement

The results demonstrate that the most effective decisions are made with a combination of statistical reliability and high economic efficiency. Analysis of the presented cases allows us to formulate the following patterns: an observed improvement does not guarantee its sustainability; the p- value is a tool for assessing the reliability of results; management decisions must consider both statistical and economic indicators; and errors in data interpretation can lead to significant economic losses.

The cases examined show that in order to make effective management decisions, it is necessary to consider not only the statistical significance of the results, but also their economic interpretation.

A quality management system regulated by ISO 9001:2015 places particular emphasis on process performance and its impact on the overall performance of the organization. However, in practice, situations often arise where statistically significant changes are not accompanied by significant economic benefits, and vice versa.

This necessitates a comprehensive approach that includes: statistical evaluation (p- value); economic evaluation (ROI, costs, benefits); management interpretation of the results.

One of the key indicators of economic performance is ROI (return on investment). This metric allows one to assess the economic viability of investments in process improvements (for example, the implementation of digital technologies). When making management decisions, it is important to consider two aspects:

Criterion	Meaning
p- value	reliability of the result
ROI	economic feasibility

Based on their combination, four typical situations can be identified:

Scenario 1: p- value ↓ / ROI ↑.

Statistically significant and cost-effective result.

Ideal option. Scaling the solution is recommended.

Scenario 2: p- value ↓ / ROI ↓.

The result is reliable, but not cost-effective.

Possible reasons: high cost of implementation, low effect.

Solution: cost optimization, technology revision.

Scenario 3: p- value ↑ / ROI ↑.

There is an economic effect, but there is no statistical significance.

Reason: Insufficient data. Solution: Continue analysis, do not make a final decision.

Scenario 4: p- value ↑ / ROI ↓.

There is no credibility or economic benefit. Solution: abandon the project.

Management decision errors. Ignoring statistical or economic assessments can lead to the following errors:

Mistake 1. "Illusion of improvement." A decrease in the indicator is observed, but the p- value is high. Risk: making a false decision.

Mistake 2. "Ignoring the benefits." There is statistical significance, but the economic impact is not analyzed. Risk: ineffective investment.

Mistake 3. "Focusing only on numbers." Decisions are made solely on the p- value. Production realities and expert opinions are ignored.

The link between economic and statistical evaluation is realized through the PDCA cycle.

Conceptual model:

PDCA stage	Statistical tool	Economic instrument
Plan	Formulating hypotheses	Calculating the expected ROI
Do	Data collection	Cost analysis
Check	p- value, SPC	Economic impact assessment
Act	Process adjustments	Scaling decision

At QARMET JSC, decision-making must consider the cost of defects; impact on productivity; investment costs; and sustainability of the effect. This enables a shift from local improvements to strategic quality management.

The obtained results confirm that the application of statistical methods within the framework of ISO 9001:2015 allows for greater objectivity in management decision-making. However, statistical significance should not be considered in isolation from economic efficiency. In the context of Industry 4.0, the integration of data analytics, digital platforms, and economic models for performance assessment is particularly relevant. The practice of QARMET JSC demonstrates that the use of intelligent quality control systems helps reduce defects, accelerate management decisions, and improve the sustainability of the production system.

Risks of misinterpretation of data:

Error type	Cause	Consequences
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False positive decision	Ignoring p- value	Unjustified investments
False negative decision	Insufficient sample size	Loss of potential effect
Ignoring ROI	Focus only on statistics	Economically ineffective projects
Ignoring expert opinion	Automation of decisions	Decreased stability of the QMS

The study showed that data-driven decision-making is becoming a key factor in improving the effectiveness of quality management systems in the context of industrial digital transformation. The use of statistical methods enables a shift from reactive quality control to proactive process management based on objective quantitative metrics and analytics.

It has been established that the use of statistical process control tools facilitates the timely detection of deviations, reduces product defects, and improves the stability of production processes. Thus, a statistical approach to quality management serves not only as a control tool but also as a strategic mechanism for enhancing the competitiveness of an enterprise in the context of Industry 4.0. Prospects for further research are related to the development of predictive analytics, digital twins, and the integration of Big Data technologies into quality management processes.

LITERATURE

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